

ISic3455

I.Sicily inscription 3455

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2014.10.30 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Menae

Place of origin (modern)

Mineo

Provenance

Territory of Mineo, probably contrada Favarotta (37.307741,
14.710805)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Mineo, Museo Civico Corrado
Tamburino Merlini, inventory 5200

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644933

EDCS 70900741

Bibliography

Cordano, F. 2014. Materiale vecchio e nuovo dalla Sicilia orientale. In Alfieri Tonini, T., Struffolino, S.(eds.), *Dinamiche culturali ed etniche nella Sicilia orientale dall'età classica all'epoca ellenistica*. Trento. pp. 105-111. At 109 no.12

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